

Failure Mechanisms of Instability-Assisted 3D Printed Microstructured Fibers

Frédéric P. Gosselin, Shibo Zou, Daniel Therriault

Laboratory for Multiscale Mechanics (LM²),
Department of Mechanical Engineering, École Polytechnique de Montréal,
P.O. Box 6079, Station Centre-Ville, Montréal, Québec, Canada, H3C 3A7
frederick.gosselin@polymtl.ca, www.fgosselin.com

ABSTRACT

We developed a technique using a flow instability to fabricate tough micro-structured fibres inspired by the molecular structure of the spider silk protein. To fabricate micro-structured fibres with various mechanical properties, we yield the control of their exact geometry to the liquid rope coiling instability. Using a fused deposition modelling 3D printer outside its normal parameter operating range, we flow a filament of viscous molten polymer towards a substrate moving perpendicularly at a slower velocity than the filament flows. This gives rise to periodic meanders and stitch patterns of the filament. As the polymer cools, the filament solidifies into a fiber with a geometry bestowed by the instability. Uniaxial tension tests performed on coiling fibres show five different types of failure. We investigate the occurrence of these different types of failures with respect to the length of the specimens tested. Depending on the length of the fibre, different failure modes are observed (torsion, bending, tensile, even dynamic). Therefore, we perform a comprehensive stress analysis of the unfolding process of a single coiling loop to understand the cause of early breakage.

With this study, we seek to understand the failure mechanisms of instability-assisted 3D printed fibres. This fabrication technology offers the potential of tailoring the mechanical properties of fibres by manipulating their micro-structure. We hope that by understanding how the fibres fail, we will be able to optimise their fabrication and obtain the best mechanical properties in terms of toughness and stiffness. These fibres could then be embedded in a composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Spider capture silk outperforms most synthetic materials in terms of specific toughness [1]. This toughness can be explained in part by the protein structure of spider silk: the protein coils on itself like a helical spring where each loop is bound to its neighbours by hydrogen bonds [2]. These hydrogen bonds act like *sacrificial bonds*, meaning that they must be broken and sacrificed before the backbone of the protein can be unwound, stretched and broken [3]. Breaking all of these sacrificial bonds, unwinding and stretching the protein structure requires lots of work, hence making spider capture silk extremely tough.

There is much interest in mimicking this mechanism of sacrificial bonds in synthetic materials. One inherent difficulty in mimicking natural material is achieving their hierarchical micro-structure. Here, we developed a technique using a flow instability to fabricate micro-structured fibres inspired by the molecular structure of the spider silk protein [4]. This fabrication technique relies on the “fluid-mechanical sewing machine” [5, 6]. This instability causes a thread of honey to wiggle as it buckles when hitting a surface.

Similarly, using a fused deposition modelling 3D printer outside its normal parameter operating range, we have shown that this instability can be observed for a filament of viscous molten polymer [4]. By extruding a filament towards a substrate moving perpendicularly at a slower velocity than the filament flows (Figure 1 a), the filament gets compressed and buckles repetitively giving rise to periodic meanders and stitch patterns (Figure 1 b-f). As the polymer cools, the filament solidifies into a fibre with a geometry bestowed by the instability. Moreover, for some patterns (Figure 1 b-d), the fibre loops and welds to itself. When pulling on these fibres in a tensile test, we showed that these welds behave as sacrificial bonds, mimicking the spider silk toughening mechanism.

Figure 1: Schematic of the fabrication process (a): a molten thread of PLA is extruded onto a conveyor belt and forms different instability patterns. The observed instability patterns are: (b) coiling; (c) coiling; (d) alternating; (e) meandering; and (f) straight. Tensile tests are performed on individual fibers (g).

In ref. [4], we showed that the instability-assisted 3D printing technique could be used to tailor the mechanical properties of fibres. By picking the right pattern, one could obtain a fibre more or less tough and more or less stiff. However, it was observed that some fibres broke prematurely, i.e., their backbone failed before every sacrificial bond broke, before every loop could unwind. The present study seeks to investigate these premature failures. We do so with a combination of tensile tests and finite element method (FEM) simulations.

2 METHODOLOGY

To fabricate micro-structured fibres with various mechanical properties, we yield the control of their exact geometry to the fluid mechanical sewing machine instability.

A filament of poly(lactic acid) (PLA) (MakerBot PLA orange) was fused at 230°C . The filament was extruded at velocity V_E through the printing head of a commercial 3D printer (Makerbot replicator). The thread solidified as it cooled in the ambient air (22°C) and was collected by a conveyor belt moving at a speed V_B .

Fibres were tested in a universal tensile machine (MTS Insight) with a 100N load cell and pneumatic clamps. All fibres tested were made with the same coiling pattern. Fibres of 8 different lengths were tested to include specimens with 1, 2, 3... and 8 loops. For each length, 10 specimens were tested.

Quasi-static FEM simulations were performed with ANSYS 15. The Multilinear Isotropic Hardening Model was used to represent the behaviour of PLA. Coiling fibres were modelled mostly with beam elements except at the tip of the loops where volumetric elements had to be used because the large distortion encountered made the simulations unstable when beam elements were used throughout. Rigid regions were used to connect the beam elements to the volumetric elements. Fibres with a coiling geometry were simulated. Two coils were considered. At one end, all six degrees of freedom were fixed to zero, whereas at the other end, a translation along the axis of the fibre was imposed and all five other degrees of freedom were fixed to zero. The sacrificial bonds were simulated with multi-point constraints (MPC), coupling two nodes together. When a threshold tensile force was applied on the fibre, the MPC was killed to simulate the breaking of the bond. The analysis considered both geometrical and material non-linearities.

Figure 2: Tensile test of a coiling fiber, comparison of experiments and non-linear FEM simulation. The shape of the fibre as it seen to unwind in the experiment and the simulation is shown above the plot.

3 RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the tensile force measured upon stretching a coiling fibre. It bears the typical sawtooth form of fibres exhibiting sacrificial bonds. The force increases linearly at first then suddenly drops when the first sacrificial bond breaks. As the loop unwinds the force increases smoothly until it reaches the threshold force and the second sacrificial bond breaks at around 130% strain. The fibre backbone finally breaks at 240% strain.

In order to perform the FEM simulations, the Multilinear Isotropic Hardening Model is fitted on data from tensile tests on straight fibres. The numerical FEM simulation matches well the experiment in Figure 2. Note that the threshold breaking force of the sacrificial bonds at 22.5 N is the only fitting parameter used. Above the plot of Figure 2, a comparison of the observed shape of the unwinding fibre with the simulated one is shown. The FEM shape is coloured with the von Mises stress which highlight considerable distributed stress (shown in red) in the unwound loop. The shape agreement between the simulation and the test is appreciable.

Figure 2 displays the desired behaviour of the fibres, i.e., all sacrificial bonds break before the backbone break. For the specific pattern tested, if longer specimens with more than two loops are tested, it is not all bonds that open before the fibre backbone fails. Figure 3 shows the five types of failures observed. Tensile failure (Figure 3 a) occurs after all sacrificial bonds have broken. Torsion failure displays a 45° break and can occur away from a former bond site (Figure 3 b) or where a broken bond left a scar (Figure 3 c). When a cusp forms at the top of a loop, a bending failure can be observed (Figure 3 d). For some specimens, a dynamic failure can be observed where the fibre backbone fails in a fraction of second after a sacrificial bond breaks and the hidden length is released.

Figure 4 shows how changing the number of bonds tested—which amounts to changing the length of the specimen—influences the observed types of failures. Here, the fibre pattern stays the same, only the length of the specimen is changed. For this specific geometry of fibres, the axial failure could only be observed for short specimens with only one loop and one bond. For short specimens, the bending failure is the most frequently observed, but for specimens with more than one loop, it is the torsion failure that is most common. The dynamic failure can be observed on long specimens with six or more loops.

Having validated our FEM approach in Figure 2, we turn again to the simulation to learn more about the occurrence of the different failure modes. The contour plots of Figure 5 show the curvature and the torsional strain of the fibre along its length as it is pulled. These preliminary results show that curvature gets tighter at the top of the loops prior to bond breaking. If the loop fails to unwind, a cusp may form and the fibre fails in bending. If this does not happen, then twist concentrates at the tip of the loop when

Figure 3: Failure modes observed for coiling fibers: (a) tensile failure; (b) torsion failure; (c) bond site defect failure; (d) bending failure; (e) dynamic failure.

Figure 4: Occurrences of different failure modes in function of the length of the specimens. A batch of 10 identical specimens were tested for each number of bonds.

Figure 5: Representation of the curvature and torsional strain along the length of the coiled fiber as it is stretched and unwound.

it is unwinding.

4 CONCLUSION

With this study, we seek to understand the failure mechanisms of instability-assisted 3D printed fibres. This fabrication technology offers the potential of tailoring the mechanical properties of fibres by manipulating their micro-structure. We hope that by understanding how the fibres fail, we will be able to optimise their fabrication and obtain the best mechanical properties in terms of toughness and stiffness. These fibres represent a highly curious system which can exhibit five different types of failure. Understanding how these failure modes interplay could allow us to better tailor the fibre patterns to fabricate tough fibres.

In the near future, we want to extend our FEM analysis to understand why identical specimens break in different modes. We plan on testing the effect of scale as well as slenderness on the occurrence of the different failures. We also want to deploy a fast camera to observe the dynamic failure mode.

It is understood that the academic system we study is based on cheap and easy-to-work-with PLA, and that this polymer possess low performance mechanical properties. However, the fluid-mechanical sewing machine used to fabricate the fibres and the analysis we perform here could work for any other type of polymer. The idea here is to improve upon the base mechanical properties of a given polymer by micro-structuring it. We could envision adapting our methodology to Peek or Nylon or any other thermoplastic with better mechanical properties. We could then imagine incorporating these tailored micro-structured fibres into high performance composites.

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